

AN AUTOMATED PROCEDURE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF
SATELLITE EARTH STATION COORDINATION AREAS

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ABSTRACT

The five basic interference interactions possible with satellite communication systems are presented. One of these, the interaction between an Earth station and the terrestrial environment, is the primary interest of this paper.

Earth station coordination contours are required as part of the international frequency notification process, and are used for determining if coordination with other administrations is required to preclude interference between a proposed new satellite earth station and the terrestrial environment.

An automated procedure for generating Earth station coordination contours, by using the procedures of ITU Appendix 28, and its computer implementation at NTIA, form the topics of this paper. The considerable manpower savings resulting from the automation is also discussed.

I. The Five Basic Interference Interactions

In the analysis of the EMC of satellite systems, (satellites and their associated earth terminals) there are five possible ways for interference to occur. They are:

One satellite may cause or experience interference to or from another satellite.

A satellite may cause or experience interference to or from an Earth station that is part of another system.

An Earth station that is part of one system may cause or experience interference to or from the Earth station of another system.

A satellite may cause or experience interference to or from an unrelated terrestrial communication station.

An earth station can similarly cause or experience interference to or from an unrelated terrestrial station.

Each of these interactions is diagrammed in Figure 1.

II. Earth Station VS Environment

The last of these interactions, the Earth station to terrestrial environment case, is an important factor to consider when planning a new Earth station.

A. What Is The Environment?

The terrestrial environment mentioned above includes any radio communications stations on the Earth's surface that are not part of the satellite system. When considering the potential for International Interference, i.e. interference to or from the stations of another country, it is often not possible to determine the radio environment in another country, so estimated equipment parameters must be used. Typical equipment parameters have been agreed upon internationally, and these typical characteristics define a standard environment for use in international coordination.

B. What Is Coordination?

The coordination area is the area associated with an Earth station outside of which a terrestrial station sharing the same frequency band neither causes nor is subject to interfering emissions greater than a permissible level. Note that a station inside the coordination area may or may not cause or experience interference to or from the Earth station, but a station outside the area definitely will not. So the goal of a coordination model is to identify those terrestrial stations if any, that should be analyzed in detail. The coordination process, then, involves the exchange of detailed system data between the countries concerned, and possibly specific one-to-one analyses of the interactions identified by the coordination model.

C. Need For Coordination

The international Telecommunication Union (ITU) Radio Regulations state (Art. 11, Sec. III, §16., No. 1106) that before an administration...brings into use...an Earth station, ...in a frequency band

allocated with equal rights to space and terrestrial radiocommunication services, it shall effect coordination with each administration whose territory lies ...within the coordination area of the planned Earth station. In order to determine what territory lies within the coordination area of an Earth station, a coordination contour defining the area must be generated.

D. Define The Earth Station

The generation of a coordination contour is generally similar to an inter-system EMC analysis, so only gross system parameters are needed. The important/defining characteristics of the Earth station are:

- 1) Its location (geographic coordinates),
- 2) Transmitter output power,
- 3) Receiver noise temperature,
- 4) Antenna gain characteristics,
- 5) Frequency of operation, and
- 6) Operating procedure.

III. Appendix 28

A. Background

Appendix 28 of the ITU Radio Regulations defines a procedure for the generation of Earth station coordination contours.

The Appendix 28 procedure is required by the ITU for use in the international arena, and it provides a standard procedure that will insure that each agency or administration obtains the same result. It also establishes a standard procedure for the coordination of domestic satellite systems within the domestic environment.

Appendix 28 provides for the consideration of two cases, namely, transmitting Earth stations (capable of interfering with terrestrial stations), and receiving Earth stations (capable of being interfered with by terrestrial stations).

Since the objective of the Appendix 28 is to provide a cull model rather than a detailed prediction model, the most conservative assumptions are made. This leads to a worst-case analysis. For example, terrestrial station antennas are assumed always to be aimed directly toward the Earth station.

B. Procedure

The Appendix 28 procedure is based on the general EMC analysis method and the INR (Interference to Noise Ratio) equation. The procedural concepts and assumptions are as follows.

The required attenuation to insure that interference may be considered negligible is basically the difference between the transmitter output power level and the permissible level of interfering signal power. Since propagation path losses are usually defined as the attenuation between isotropic antennas, the effective antenna gains at both ends of the circuit are included explicitly. The minimum basic transmission loss is given by:

$$LP = PT + GT + GR - PR$$

where:

LP = Minimum basic transmission loss(dB)

GT = Transmitter antenna gain (dBi) in the direction of the receiver

GR = Receiver antenna gain (dBi) in the direction of the transmitter

PR = Permissible level of interfering signal power (dBw)

PT = Transmitter output power (dBw)

PT and PR are defined for the same reference RF bandwidth and PR and LP are defined for the same time percentage reliability. The Earth station antenna gain is taken to be the gain in the direction of the physical horizon at the azimuth under consideration. Actual antenna patterns are used if available, otherwise CCIR antenna pattern models are used to determine the Earth station antenna gain. The antenna gain of the terrestrial stations is always the maximum (mainbeam) gain.

The equation below is used to determine the permissible level of interference.

$$PR = 10\text{LOG}(KTB) + J + M(P) - W$$

where:

10LOG(KTB) is the noise level of the receiver,

J is the long term (20% of the time) allowable interference to noise ratio (INR),

M(P) is the interference margin between short term and long term allowable interference levels,

W is a modulation correction factor, dependant on the characteristics of the desired signal and of the interfering signal. The parameter W is positive when the interfering signal would cause more degradation than thermal noise.

Since actual characteristics of receiving terrestrial stations are not known when a coordination contour is being prepared, estimated typical values are used. These values are given in Table I of Appendix 28.

Standardized parameters, typical of receiving Earth station, are given in Table II of Appendix 28, with the exception of receiver noise level, which is unique to the system under consideration.

C. Path Loss Models

Two significantly different attenuation mechanisms are considered, by using a different analysis for each. They are: attenuation of signals subject

to tropospheric propagation via near great circle paths, Mode 1, and attenuation of signals subject to scatter due to hydrometeors (rainscatter), Mode 2.

The Mode 1 path loss model is derived from a CCIR prediction method for path losses that considers ducting and superrefraction, and includes a correction factor to account for diffraction losses over a single obstacle.

The result of the tropospheric propagation model depends on the frequency, terrain roughness, atmospheric composition, and horizon elevation angle.

For the determination of the above parameters, the Earth has been divided into three radio climatic zones (A,B,&C): Zone A encompasses all land areas. Zone B basically includes bodies of water at latitudes greater than 23.5N or S. Zone C is bodies of water in the tropics, with latitudes less than 23.5N or S. Values of terrain roughness and atmospheric composition in each of these zones is given in Appendix 28. Frequency and the local horizon angles are unique to the Earth station under consideration and must be provided for each analysis.

If the coordination distance calculated extends through more than one radio climatic zone, then a special procedure for the analysis of mixed paths is followed.

The model for rainscatter propagation assumes a path geometry that is substantially different from that of the great circle propagation mechanisms. Energy is scattered in all directions equally by rain, so interference may result from many different angles.

For use when actual climatological data are not available, (as in most cases), the world has been divided into 5 basic rain-climatic zones. Typical average rainfall characteristics are specified for each zone.

The transmitted signal is assumed to be scattered in all directions equally from a rain cell in the Earth station antenna mainbeam.

The coordination contour, then, is a circle centered on the hypothetical rain cell. This circle is offset from the Earth station location in the direction of the antenna mainbeam, by an amount dependant on the Earth station antenna elevation angle, and the average rain cell altitude.

D. Manual Methods

The manual generation of Appendix 28 coordination contours is a very tedious and time intensive task. The following aspects of the procedure are especially so.

1) With each new problem, the interference parameters and typical terrestrial station parameters must be looked up in tables, and extracted for use in the calculations.

2) The distances from the Earth station to the radio zone boundaries must be determined along all of the azimuths around the Earth station. This involves attempting to plot radials around the Earth station on a map, and measuring distances on the map, then converting map distances to real distances.

3) The location of the Earth station must be found on the rain zone map, and a determination made as to the zone in which it falls. This in itself is often a difficult determination, as the world map is only 2x4 inches. The rainfall parameters must then be looked up in another table.

4) The horizon elevation angles in each of the azimuthal directions of interest must be determined, either from graphs of site survey data, or from topographic maps. In either case, much manual point selection from graphs is required.

5) Most tedious is the repetitive performance of calculations. The above described calculations for antenna gain in the direction of interest, required basic transmission loss, and path loss models must be recalculated for each of the azimuthal directions to be considered. For best accuracy, calculations should be made for each of the 360 degree radials, however, when manual methods are used, contours are generally approximated by calculating points on radials spaced 5 or 10 degrees apart. This still means that some 36-72 complete sets of calculations must be done for each contour.

6) Once the coordination distances in all azimuthal directions have been calculated, they must be plotted to scale on a political map of the vicinity of the earth station.

E. Need To Automate

We at NTIA determined that there was a need for automation of the coordination contour production process, for the following reasons.

1) NTIA maintains and publishes a set of coordination contours for all US Government Earth stations, all of which must be recomputed in accordance with the new procedures adopted by the ITU at the World Administrative Radio Conference (WARC 79). There are currently over 300 contours in this set.

2) Additionally, coordination contours must be generated for all new and proposed Earth stations, as part of the coordination process. With our limited manpower, we needed a simple and rapid way of obtaining contours.

IV. The Automated Procedure

With the firmly established need in mind, the automated procedure was specified to meet the following requirements.

A. Requirements

It must be easy for a non-computer-specialist to operate, from start to finish. It must also be tolerant of human beings (user friendly).

It must be understandable. We wanted someone with a reasonable background and familiarity with Appendix 28 to be able to operate the program, without constant references to a book or expert.

We wanted to automate all functions that could be automated, while saving for the operator only those functions and decisions that must be done by humans.

We wanted to allow as much flexibility as possible in the running of the program, and in the presentation of results.

The process needed to be repeatable, with minor parameter changes, without starting from scratch.

We found it desirable to calculate the auxiliary contours at the same time as the calculation of the original coordination contours. An auxiliary contour is determined the same way as the corresponding coordination contour for propagation Mode 1, but with one difference. An auxiliary contour is calculated by using terrestrial station interference sensitivity or EIRP values which are 5,10,15,20 dB etc. lower than the value used for the coordination contour.

Finally, we wanted to design a program that did not throw up its hands in despair at the first sign of data incompleteness. Instead, it was designed to fill in the blanks whenever possible.

B. Two Part Implementation

The automation was implemented in two basic parts 1) A batch-type calculation part, and 2) an interactive data gathering and formatting part.

A program written by the Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Center (ECAC) in Annapolis, Maryland, provides the basic calculation structure. This program receives rigidly formatted punched-card input, and performs the repetitive calculations.

Our implementation adds to the calculation structure the interactive data gathering and data formatting, as well as the flexibility and repeatability. Shown in Figure 2 is a system overview in flowchart form.

C. Implementation Details

The implementation is in ASCII Fortran 77 computer language, on the NTIA UNIVAC 1108 mainframe

computer. It makes use of our existing terrain files, graphics and plotting package, and political boundary file.

The program gathers its data by asking questions of an engineer at a CRT terminal. If any question is not understood, the engineer may type HELP, and the computer will give a more complete description of the data required. After gathering several basic facts about the Earth station, the computer calculates approximations of other parameters, and looks up the interference parameters and typical terrestrial station characteristics for the frequency band given.

The computer also accesses our topographic data base to obtain horizon elevation angle data. The distances to radio zone boundaries (coastlines) are computed along each of 360 radials, by using a computer-stored map of the zones. The computer then allows the engineer the option of viewing all of the approximations and looked up values, and of replacing them with known values if desired.

Following each question displayed on the CRT is a parenthesis () containing a recovery answer for that question. This recovery value will be used if the engineer fails to provide a better answer. Otherwise the value entered in response to the question is used in computation.

Once all the data have been gathered for a problem, an option is available for looping back through the questions to set up a second problem. When this is done, all of the parameters of the first problem are saved, and are used as the recovery values for the second problem.

When data gathering is finished, the data are formatted and written on disc files in the format required by the batch calculation program.

Provision is made for permanent storage, in a uniquely named disc file, of all data as well as all calculated results and outputs. The entire run can be recreated from this stored file at a later time, without re-entry of data.

The batch calculation program can be run at any time by invoking the previously stored data.

There are four major forms of output from the programs. Two of these are calculation results from the batch program. The others are graphic outputs generated by our pre-existing graphics package by using the calculation results.

The main output of the calculation program is a printout listing all of the input data, and listing the coordination distances along each of the 360 azimuth radials.

In addition, tables of the coordination distances (contour tables) are written in machine readable form on disc files, and are saved for later use in contour plotting. At present, contour tables are written for each of six contours: The mode 1 propagation contour, the Mode 2 (rainscatter)

contour, the coordination contour (maximum of modes 1 & 2), and three auxiliary contours.

Through the use of our calcomp plotter, and graphics software, plots of any combination of contours can be obtained. The provisions for generating plots are made by the interactive part of the program, so plot generation is essentially automatic. Plots are of a standard size, and are labeled, ready for publication. See Figure 3 for an example.

The capability is available to view a contour plot on the screen of a tektronics graphics terminal at any time. This allows for previewing of plots to insure quality, as well as review of previously generated and stored coordination contours at any time.

D. Meets Requirements

The programs, as currently implemented, fulfill all of our basic requirements, and the system performs well.

E. Limitations, Shortfalls

We are currently limited to analysis of fixed Earth stations. For the future, some provision may be required for mobile Earth stations. We are also limited by our terrain data and radio zone data to analysis of Earth stations located in the USA.

V. Person-Power Savings

The implementation of the automated method has provided NTIA with a considerable savings in time and labor.

A. Time For Manual Contours

The manual method required an average of 2 man-days to generate and verify a contour. By using this method, more than two years would have been required to produce the 300+ new contours.

B. Estimated Time Savings

The automated procedure is estimated to require only about 2 man-hours to complete each contour. This represents an 87% improvement over the manual method.

C. Experience

Our experience with the program so far has proven that it is, indeed, as efficient as it was estimated that it would be. With data at hand, as many as a dozen jobs can be entered in one morning at a terminal. Our biggest problem has been that we sometimes overwhelm the computer center with the large number of jobs submitted at one time.

VI. Conclusion

An automated procedure for the production of coordination contours has been presented. The implementation of this automation has meant improved quality outputs at a lower cost in time and labor than was previously available.

- A - Satellite-Satellite
- B - Satellite-Earth Station
- C - Earth Station-Earth Station
- D - Satellite-Terr. Environment
- E - Earth Station-Terr. Environment

Figure 1. Diagram of Basic Interference Interactions.

Figure 2. System Overview

Figure 3. Example Contour Plot